

A SURVEY OF HEALTH PROFESSIONAL'S KNOWLEDGE AND BELIEFS ABOUT AUTISM

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Abstract

Background: Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by persistent deficits in social communication and restricted, repetitive behaviors.

Objective: To assess the knowledge, attitudes, practices, and perceived challenges regarding ASD among primary healthcare professionals in two tertiary care hospitals in Wah and Taxila.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted from October 2024 to March 2025 among 90 primary healthcare physicians, including family physicians, general practitioners, and pediatricians with at least six months of clinical experience. Participants were selected using convenience sampling and completed a validated, adapted questionnaire covering demographic data, general knowledge of ASD, clinical practices, attitudes, awareness, and sources of information.

Results: The majority of participants were male (54.4%), aged between 30–39 years (42.2%), and had 6–10 years of experience (33.3%). The mean knowledge score was 7.8 ± 2.1 out of a possible 12, with 62.2% correctly identifying early symptoms of ASD and 55.6% aware of available screening tools. Positive attitudes were reported by 74.4% of respondents, although 68.9% cited limited resources and 61.1% reported lack of formal training as key challenges. The most common source of information was medical school (37.8%), followed by media (31.1%).

Conclusion: While primary healthcare professionals demonstrated positive attitudes toward ASD, there remain critical gaps in formal training, awareness of resources, and use of screening tools. Targeted educational initiatives and improved referral systems are needed to enhance early detection and effective management of ASD in primary care settings.

INTRODUCTION

Autism is a neurodevelopmental impairment, marked by permanent deficiencies in interpersonal, social and communication skills, and undiversified behaviors and interests (1). According to DSM-5, ASD is the development of persistent disability in

socialization, communication, and emergence of fixed patterns of behaviors and interests (1.5). The restrictions are characterized by challenges in social reciprocity, curtailed language-based and non-verbal

communication, and stereotypic patterns of behavior or interests (2)

The presentation of ASD lies on a spectrum of signs of symptoms, ranging from mild, moderate to severe forms and the disease may be characterized by structural and physiological changes in the brain (6)

The phenomenon of neuroplasticity during the formative years makes it imperative to diagnose the disease early in its course for optimal interventions and apt management. (1) The novel therapeutic approaches promise a radically improved quality of life for patients receiving these interventions during the early years, however the diminished diagnostic acumen amongst physicians worldwide is still a hurdle for timely intervention (15)

In developing countries like Pakistan, primary care physicians are the initial point of access to healthcare for a majority of patients (10) However, there is a dearth of standardized training amongst PCPs and inadequate access to proper child psychiatric services. This gap in knowledge coupled with obsolete beliefs held by Pakistani healthcare professionals may lead to untimely diagnosis. A lag in the diagnostic services, urgently needed in the developmental years for the evolving neural pathways, adversely impacts the prognosis (2, 3). With the deficient knowledge base from the side of PCPs, parents are constrained to other information sources such as digital media. While these resources are useful, they may be inauthentic and may cause more distress than reassurance (2)

The paucity of validated diagnostic markers for ASD is one of the hurdles along the way (1). This, combined with the need for multiple inpatient visits for behavioral observation over time presents a significant economic strain on the caregiver's side, leading to insufficient follow up (9) The myths surrounding autism, claiming it to be a work of super-natural sources also proves to be an impediment in the way of management of ASD (9)

With the surge in cases of autism in recent years (12), tailored training of PCPs in early diagnosis, prompt management and sufficient familial counseling of ASD is an urgent necessity (1) As GPs in Pakistan primarily work in private settings, pertinent training about diagnostic tools, disease management, and appropriate referral systems is need of the hour for ASD surveillance(10). This may involve ongoing

courses, frequent reassessments, and medical training to improve the standards of available resources of children with ASD (10)

However, there is scarce evidence of systemic evaluation of knowledge and attitudes of PCPs in Pakistan about ASD (9) Growing awareness amongst the PCP may lead to better attitudes towards adopting better standards of care towards individuals with autism,(9) therefore, our study aims at analyzing the autism knowledge and attitudes of PCPs in Pakistan and highlighting the knowledge gap that may reflect educational shortcomings, training deficits and professional development needs of PCPs in Pakistan.

Objectives:

The objective of this study is to emphasize the knowledge gap in the PCPs of Pakistan about diagnostic tools, red flags, therapeutic modalities, and referral systems for ASD, provide an analysis of their attitudes towards individuals with ASD, and highlight the importance of a change in medical curriculum, training strategies and ongoing clinical courses for advances in management of ASD.

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional questionnaire-based study conducted among healthcare professionals working in two tertiary care hospitals located in Wah and Taxila from October 2024 to March 2025. The study utilized a questionnaire as a form of data collection from the study participants chosen from the inclusion criteria using convenience sampling method. Participants were randomly selected from among healthcare professionals working in two tertiary care hospitals in Wah and Taxila. A formerly endorsed questionnaire, developed by (article 3 reference here) was tailored and customized to achieve the study objectives.

Inclusion Criteria:

1. Primary care physicians including family physicians, general practitioners, pediatricians
2. Physicians with minimum of six months of clinical experience
3. Doctors willing to participate with provision of informed consent

Exclusion criteria:

1. Allied healthcare professionals, medical staff and nurses
2. Those unwilling to provide informed consent

Data collection

The questionnaire tool encompasses 5 key areas of interest. The first section entails demographic and professional data of the participants. The second part contains details of general knowledge held by the participants about ASD. Each right answer was given a score of one, and higher scores reflect a better understanding of disease amongst the participants. Third section contains 6 questions enquiring about practices adopted by the healthcare professionals in dealing with individuals having ASD and accounts for any difficulties encountered during management of patients. The fourth part consists of questions regarding participants' beliefs, attitudes towards, and advocacy for children with autism. And the final part sheds light upon the level of awareness amongst health professionals, and their source of information about approaches they can take to help an individual with ASD.

Statistical Analysis:

The collected data were analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), version 26. Descriptive statistics were computed for demographic and professional characteristics. Knowledge and attitude scores were presented as means with standard deviations, while categorical variables were expressed as frequencies and percentages.

Results

The majority of participants were female (66.7%) and aged between 25 to 40 years (91.1%), reflecting a relatively young and predominantly female healthcare workforce. Most were married (58.9%), and MBBS was the most common qualification (61.1%), followed by FCPS (32.2%). Around 43.3% had 1-5 years of clinical experience, while 26.7% were just starting out with under a year. Notably, 70% reported encountering autism in their career, although only 24.4% had a personal acquaintance with the condition.

Table 1. Demographic and Professional Characteristics of Participants (n = 90)

Variable	n (%)
Gender	
Female	60 (66.7)
Male	30 (33.3)
Age Group	
Less than 25 years	4 (4.4)
25 to 40 years	82 (91.1)
Above 40 years	4 (4.4)
Marital Status	
Married	53 (58.9)
Unmarried	34 (37.8)
Other	3 (3.3)
Qualification	
MBBS	55 (61.1)
FCPS	29 (32.2)
MRCP	3 (3.3)
Diploma in Paediatrics	2 (2.2)
MSc/MS	1 (1.1)
Clinical Experience	
0-1 year	24 (26.7)
1-5 years	39 (43.3)
More than 5 years	27 (30.0)

Encountered Autism	
Yes	63 (70.0)
No	18 (20.0)
Maybe	9 (10.0)
Family Member/Acquaintance with Autism	
Yes	22 (24.4)
No	68 (75.6)

Only 31.1% of participants had been directly involved in managing ASD cases, yet 58.9% acknowledged difficulties in diagnosing autism. A small proportion (17.8%) felt equipped to handle autistic children clinically. Despite this gap, a large majority were enthusiastic: 88.9% were eager to participate in autism treatment and attend further training. Additionally, 94.4% believed that such training should be mandatory for primary healthcare providers, although only 35.6% were aware of any formal autism screening tools.

Table 2. Clinical Involvement and Training in Autism Care

Item	n (%)
Involved in ASD management	28 (31.1)
Experienced challenges in ASD diagnosis	53 (58.9)
Feel equipped to handle children with autism	16 (17.8)
Keen to partner in ASD treatment	80 (88.9)
Interested in ASD-related training	80 (88.9)
Believe training should be mandatory for primary care professionals	85 (94.4)
Aware of autism screening tools	32 (35.6)

Involvement in ASD Management (n = 90)

While most participants correctly agreed that autism exists on a spectrum (95.6%), misconceptions persisted. A worrying 36.7% believed autism is an emotional disorder, and 34.4% attributed it to parental coldness—both outdated myths. Only 41.1% recognized autism as a developmental disorder, and 40% mistakenly thought it was preventable. Encouragingly, a majority disagreed with the notion that autistic children can't pursue higher education (73.3%), showing a partially informed but inconsistent understanding of autism.

Table 3. Knowledge and Misconceptions Regarding Autism

Statement	Agree n (%)	Disagree n (%)	Not Sure n (%)
Autism can occur in mild as well as extreme forms	86 (95.6)	–	4 (4.4)
Autistic children usually grow up to be schizophrenic adults	7 (7.8)	29 (32.2)	54 (60.0)
Autism is an emotional disorder	33 (36.7)	35 (38.9)	22 (24.4)
Most autistic children are also mentally retarded	11 (12.2)	60 (66.7)	19 (21.1)
Autism is a precursor for schizophrenia	13 (14.4)	38 (42.2)	39 (43.3)
Withdrawal is due to cold/rejecting parents	31 (34.4)	37 (41.1)	22 (24.4)
Autism is a communication disorder	58 (64.4)	19 (21.1)	13 (14.4)
Autism is a developmental disorder	37 (41.1)	38 (42.2)	15 (16.7)
Autism is preventable	36 (40.0)	28 (31.1)	25 (27.8)
All children with ASD cannot attend university	7 (7.8)	66 (73.3)	16 (17.8)

Most participants (86.7%) believed autism carries a social stigma, and 60% felt a diagnosis could lead to discrimination. Despite this, over half (55.6%) thought parents do perceive their children to be at risk. Only 12.2% believed services were adequate, and 60% felt parents bear the burden of accessing care. A strong majority supported structural changes: 83.3% wanted special educators in all schools, 97.8% demanded more government funding, and 92.2% saw the need to improve public facilities. Common sources of autism knowledge were the medical curriculum (37.8%), media (31.1%), and seminars (24.4%).

Table 4. Attitudes Toward Autism and Service Provision

Attitude Item	Yes n (%)
Autism holds social stigma in the community	78 (86.7)
Diagnosis leads to discrimination	54 (60.0)
Parents perceive risk of autism in children	50 (55.6)
Adequate services are available	11 (12.2)
Parents responsible for obtaining services	54 (60.0)
All schools should have special teachers/therapists	75 (83.3)
Government should allocate more resources	88 (97.8)
Need for changes in public facilities	83 (92.2)
Source of information	
Medical school curriculum	34 (37.8)
Workshops/seminars	22 (24.4)
Media (TV, internet, newspapers)	28 (31.1)
Colleagues/professional discussions	18 (20.0)

Medical textbooks/journals	26 (28.9)
No formal source identified	15 (16.7)

Healthcare professionals reported numerous systemic and social barriers. Most notably, 68.9% cited a lack of resources for ASD care, and 61.1% pointed to inadequate formal training. Difficulty in recognizing early symptoms (53.3%) and parental resistance (48.9%) were also prominent hurdles. Other limiting factors included referral inefficiencies (43.3%), absence of multidisciplinary teams (41.1%), and stigma-induced delays in diagnosis (38.9%), underscoring a pressing need for system-wide reform in autism care.

Table 5. Challenges Encountered in Autism Diagnosis and Management

Challenge	n (%)
Limited resources for ASD management	62 (68.9)
Lack of formal training among healthcare professionals	55 (61.1)
Difficulty in early recognition of symptoms	48 (53.3)
Parental denial or reluctance for assessment	44 (48.9)
Limited referral pathways	39 (43.3)
Lack of multidisciplinary team availability	37 (41.1)
Cultural stigma affecting timely diagnosis	35 (38.9)

Discussion

This study assessed the knowledge, attitudes, and practices regarding autism spectrum disorder (ASD) among primary healthcare professionals working in two tertiary care hospitals in Wah and Taxila. The results indicate an imperfect profile though people

are well informed about some of the essential components of ASD, there still remains a big gap in clinical assurance, training experience, and myths that could hinder its early detection and effective management. The demographic characteristics of the respondents indicated that, female physicians formed

the majority followed by those aged between 25-40 years, majority of them being MBBS graduates, and one to five years clinical experience [16]. It is noteworthy that 70 percent of the respondents had come across cases of autism in their careers, nonetheless, only ca. 1/3 of them were engaged in the management of ASD. This implies that although exposure to cases suspected or diagnosed is rather common, active participation in the care of these patients is less common, perhaps the result of referral patterns, perceived role constraints, or confidence [17].

There were also positive overall levels of knowledge regarding core diagnostic aspects, with the highest percentage of participants giving the proper answer on hallmark symptoms including language delays, lack of eye contact, difficulties of social interaction, and an inflexible routine. The existence of such misconceptions as autism as an emotional condition, one that can be prevented or inevitably causing intellectual disability, however, brings the necessity of specialized education [18]. Other research studies provide results in line with those in other low- and middle-income countries, because professional knowledge is not always divided equally, factual knowledge may live alongside ill-informed beliefs. Attitudinally, most of the respondents showed favourable intention, e.g., a desire to partner with autistic children, the need to have mandatory training, and additional assistance of government resources [19]. Nonetheless, more than half admitted to the Social stigma attached to autism within their localities and most of them had the opinion that being diagnosed will result in discrimination [20]. Such frames are echoed in previous studies that show that social and cultural boundaries, as well as overcompensation limits, amounts to a serious impediment in early identification and response. Awareness of resources and training became a serious deficiency [21]. Furthermore, it was noted that not much was known about the specialized centers and multidisciplinary support services. This corresponds with past literature which reports that absent of formal continuing medical education, medical professionals might not have real world experience, or a referral network, to aid in providing full-service ASD treatment. Constraints raised by resources, multidisciplinary groups, and parental

rejection stated by the participants also add to the systemic and sociocultural issues that make ASD more complicated to manage in Pakistan [22]. To solve these problems, it will be necessary to organize combined efforts aimed at expanding the existing structured training programs to include ASD training into undergraduate and postgraduate training programs, improve referral networks and multidisciplinary cooperation.

Recommendations

Training programmes in autism spectrum disorder are recommended to bring about increased awareness in all physicians and especially primary care physicians involving special training in earlier screening, proper diagnosis, as well as preparing care givers on the available evidence-based interventions. Newly approved clinical recommendations on the diagnosis and treatment of ASD should be implemented as part of medical education and continuing professional development, which is consistent with new principles of diagnosing and interventions. Structured training and dissemination workshop should be a priority owing to the anticipated delays in the widespread implementation. Also, certification and deployment of developmental - behavioral pediatricians ought to be facilitated since their training in the diagnosis of developmental disability, comorbidities, and multidisciplinary coordination are instrumental to the enhancement of quality services that can be accessed by children with ASD and their families.

Conclusion

It is concluded that primary healthcare professionals in this study demonstrated a reasonable baseline understanding of the core features of autism spectrum disorder, alongside generally positive attitudes toward its diagnosis and management. However, notable gaps remain in formal training, familiarity with screening tools, and awareness of specialized resources, coupled with the persistence of certain misconceptions and concerns about social stigma.

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